

Vaccine Beer: A Personal Healthcare Report

Christopher B. Buck¹ and Andrew R. Buck²

¹Independent Scientist, Bethesda, Maryland, USA

²Independent Scientist, Vallejo, California, USA

Abstract

Recent results publicly presented by the National Cancer Institute suggest that live yeast expressing vaccine antigens can immunize mice when delivered in the form of food. In this study, we set out to test the hypothesis that a food-based vaccine approach can be independently implemented in a home kitchen outfitted with a few thousand dollars worth of scientific equipment. Commercial brewer's yeast were engineered to express the BK polyomavirus major capsid protein as a model vaccine antigen. The yeast were then used to homebrew beer. Drinking prime and boost doses of the beer did not cause any discernible adverse effects. The results demonstrate that food manufacturers and home cooks can safely begin to explore the development of low-cost edible vaccines.

Introduction

Findings from a team at the National Cancer Institute (NCI) show that live brewer's yeast expressing vaccine antigens can be immunogenic when fed to lab mice (Buck, 2025). Food-based vaccine approaches could dramatically accelerate vaccine development, lower production costs, and improve accessibility.

In this report, we explore the hypothesis that food-based vaccine strategies can safely be extended to humans by conducting pilot self-experiments in which we ate food-grade yeast expressing a model vaccine antigen. We aim for this to be the beginning of a movement to democratize vaccine development by making it approachable for food manufacturers and home cooks (Jain, 2025; Kraushaar, 2024; Mastroianni, 2023).

To explore the live yeast vaccine approach, we ordered and recombined synthetic DNA fragments to independently generate the yeast expression plasmids described by the NCI team in a home kitchen setting. Transformed yeast were then used to produce beer containing a candidate vaccine antigen, the BK polyomavirus (BKV) major capsid protein VP1. We then drank beer containing suspended live yeast. A complete lack of significant side effects supports a self-attestation that vaccine beer qualifies for generally recognized as safe status.

BKV is a known cause of kidney, bladder, brain, and cardiovascular diseases (Lee et al., 2019; Petrogiannis-Haliotis et al., 2001; Pinto & Dobson, 2014; Robles et al., 2020; Sandler et al., 1997; Starrett et al., 2023). The aim of the self-treatments presented in this report is to reduce our individual risks of developing BKV-induced disease. The study should be viewed as an autonomous self-healthcare activity (Beauchamp & Childress, 1979).

Evaluation of the possible medical efficacy of food-based vaccine strategies will be an important future aim that can be conducted under FDA supervision. Meanwhile, food producers and consumers are free to immediately begin experimenting with the technology as a self-care tool.

Materials and Methods

Ethics statement. In our view, scientific self-experimentation in service of individual healthcare is a fundamental human right (Buck, 2022; C. B. Buck, 2023). Our viewpoint rests on a long tradition of scientists initially testing research findings on themselves and is supported by the Nuremberg Code, which explicitly allows for the possibility of ethical self-experimentation

(Hanley et al., 2019; Sills et al., 2020). This report documents individual self-healthcare activities that are insufficiently systematic or generalizable to meet the specialized legal definition of human subjects research. Detailed reasoning on this issue is presented in Appendix A.

The independent generation, consumption, and sale of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) is allowed under US law (Kramer, 2023). In our view, the GMO yeast described in this report meet federal Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) food standards. Detailed reasoning on this issue is presented in Appendix B.

The personal healthcare activities documented in this report did not use any confidential information, did not use or generate any intellectual property, and did not receive or use any government resources. The self-treatments were conducted in a home environment outside of work hours and do not in any way invoke our professional titles. The report does endorse any persons, entities, or products.

Plasmid construction. The sequence of pGustiv was downloaded from the Lab of Cellular Oncology's public [technical page](#). The sequence was synthesized as a set of cloned fragments by [GeneUniversal.com](#). Fragments were recombined in a home lab setting using traditional restriction enzyme-based cloning methods ([NEB.com](#)). Scientific equipment was purchased from [The-Odin.com](#) or via [Amazon.com](#). The finished pGustiv plasmid is publicly available for any purpose, including human studies or commercial products, under OpenMTA (Kahl et al., 2018) via [Addgene.org](#). We note that various companies, including Gene Universal, offer custom cloning services that would obviate the need for home laboratory equipment.

Yeast transformation. Detailed methods for transforming yeast and producing beer are provided in the Supplemental Methods section. In addition, we note that many companies, including Gene Universal, offer yeast transformation services.

Yeast strains of interest were transformed with pGustiv using a yeast transformation kit ([The-Odin.com](#)) and selected on YPD-agar plates ([KDmedical.com](#)) with 6 mM formaldehyde ([SigmaAldrich.com](#)). Six colonies were pooled into liquid YPD with 6 mM formaldehyde (YPD-6) and cultured with orbital shaking at 30°C for several hours prior to streaking onto malt extract plates ([OlympusMyco.com](#)). Six of the largest and most fluorescent colonies were picked into 250 µl of YPD-6 and cultured overnight. The culture was then progressively stepped up to 25 mL and 250 mL of YPD-6 in stirred Erlenmeyer flasks. Sedimented stationary phase cells from the 250 mL culture are considered a salable unit suitable for production of up to five gallons of vaccine beer.

Beer. Uninduced yeast transformed with pGustiv were cultured to near opacity in 250 mL of YPD-6 culture broth in a stirred Erlenmeyer flask. The cells were then spun down and the YPD-6 supernatant was discarded. Collected yeast cells were pitched into one liter (~one quart) of 1x Proper starter broth (OmegaYeast.com) in a 5-liter (~one gallon) continuous brewing jar (CulturesForHealth.com). The starter was cultured with stirring until expression of the green fluorescent protein (GFP) marker gene started to become evident, roughly 6-12 hours. Three liters (~3 quarts) of filtered tap water and 0.5 kg (~1 pound) of dry malt extract from a MoreBeer.com Flash Hefeweizen kit were added to the fermenter. Thirty grams (~1 ounce) of Saphir hop pellets (Artisan Hops) were steeped in a French press (Frieling) in 0.5 L (~1 pint) of boiling water. The hop tea was cooled and pressed and the filtrate was added to the fermenter. Fermentation was conducted at 24 to 34°C (75-93°F), depending on yeast strain. The home kitchen environment did not have the resources to quantitate VP1 dosing, but a rough estimate would be that, indexed to body mass, author CBB consumed roughly 1/38th of a mouse dose of induced live yeast during each roughly five-day dosing window.

Self-treatments. Both authors conducted pilot self-treatments by consuming beer on an arbitrary “best guess” convenience schedule consisting of one or two pints of beer per day.

Robust GFP expression was observed in the fermenting beer starting roughly 36 hours after pitching, at which point a pint of fresh beer with suspended live yeast was decanted from the stirred fermenter and immediately consumed at fermentation temperature. At day 3 of the fermentation, the remaining beer was distributed into one-pint flip-top bottles and carbonated by the addition of 1% (w/v) maltose (LabAlley.com).

A 20 mg dose of famotidine was taken about an hour in advance of some pints, in hopes of partially neutralizing stomach pH to promote the survival of live yeast. Sugar-free calcium carbonate [antacid tablets](#) were chewed alongside some meals, with the same rationale. Some pints were consumed on an empty stomach, while others were consumed alongside maltose-rich foods, in hopes of achieving prebiotic yeast-feeding effects (see Supplemental Methods Section B). Some of the pints were consumed together with a high-fat meal, exploring the hypothesis that the secretion of bile salts might help promote yeast lysis and release of BKV VLPs in the duodenum. In summary, the prime and boost dosing schedules consisted of one or two pints of vaccine beer per day over the course of about five days.

Results

The traditional Uniform Biological Material Transfer Agreement (UBMTA) used by the NCI team stipulates that transferred materials cannot be used in human subjects. The UBMTA also forbids further sharing or resale of transferred materials. It was therefore necessary to independently recreate the pGustiv plasmid through commercial DNA synthesis. Plasmid construction was conducted in the home kitchen of author CBB (Chris). The finished plasmid is freely [available](#) via Addgene under OpenMTA, which allows for use in humans and commercial resale (Kahl et al., 2018).

The pGustiv plasmid was initially transformed into Pakruojis Lithuanian Farmhouse Ale Yeast (White Labs [WLP4047](#)) in the home lab setting. Detailed methods are provided in the Supplemental Methods section. The transformed yeast strain was used to brew batches of roughly a gallon (4 L) of beer. Chris drank one or two pints (0.5-1 L) of the resulting vaccine beer per day over the course of about a week (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Vaccine beer in the home lab environment. The pGustiv plasmid is designed to co-express enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP) alongside the BKV VP1 vaccine antigen. GFP expression was confirmed by illuminating beer containing suspended live yeast under blue LED lights and then photographing it using a cellphone outfitted with an orange filter.

The wheat ale yeast strain (Fermentis [WB-06](#)) that comes with the Morebeer Flash Hefeweizen kit also produces a flavorful live-yeast beer. Results from the NCI team suggest that the wheat ale strain may exhibit somewhat higher and more stable vaccine antigen expression than the Pakruojis strain. Chris drank booster doses of vaccine beer made with the wheat ale strain starting at roughly week seven after the Pakruojis priming doses. A second round of booster doses using WB-06 beer was produced using the Simplified Beer Production protocol (Supplemental Methods Section A). Author ARB (Andrew) also produced and gradually consumed a gallon of beer produced using wheat ale yeast carrying pGustiv.

The NCI team's vaccination experiments with mice suggest that it's important for live yeast to shuttle the fragile vaccine antigen past the stomach acid barrier. We suspect it's also important for the yeast cells to eventually break open and release the antigen so it can directly bind the surface of specialized immune presentation cells called M cells in the small intestine (de Aizpurua & Russell-Jones, 1988). We have entertained multiple hypotheses about which foods might be most effective for facilitating these processes. We don't know which, if any, of the hypotheses are true, and some of the hypotheses are mutually exclusive. We adopted a bet-hedging strategy in which we implemented different strategies on different days (see Supplemental Methods Section B).

In healthy individuals, yeast can persist in the gut for periods of up to a few days (Pecquet et al., 1991). One hypothesis is that it might be possible to restimulate antigen expression in yeast residing in the small intestine. The MAL32 promoter system used in pGustiv is activated by maltose, so eating maltose-rich foods might restimulate antigen expression. A complicating factor is that glucose suppresses the MAL32 promoter, even in the presence of high levels of maltose. In essence, yeast cells are set up to utilize glucose as a preferred "snack food" before they activate the machinery to metabolize other sugars, such as maltose.

In pilot self-experiments, eating low-glucose/maltose-rich foods alongside vaccine beer sometimes correlated with mild bloating and flatulence, reminiscent of the familiar effects of eating beans. We also considered the hypothesis that gut fermentation might produce ethanol at levels that could produce intoxicating effects beyond what might be expected from drinking a pint of beer. We did not sense any signs of unexpected ethanol intoxication during the experiments. No other discernible side effects were detected at any point during or after the experiments.

Discussion

In terms of lives saved, vaccines have been among the most important public health interventions in human history (Berkley, 2025). Expansion of our collective vaccine arsenal to cover additional pathogens would undoubtedly save millions more lives and further avert a mountain of human misery. It is critical that we find ways to make vaccine development faster, easier, cheaper, and more broadly accessible. Food-based vaccine approaches can achieve these goals.

In the United States, there has been a growing movement to downplay the safety and efficacy of traditional vaccines, and government officials have recently begun implementing policies restricting access (O'Reilly, 2025). Food-based vaccines could help put autonomous decision-making authority back in the hands of individual Americans. Homemade vaccines might also help overcome some of the skepticism and fear surrounding traditional injected vaccines developed by pharmaceutical conglomerates.

While considering the legal requirements for IRB pre-approval (Appendix A) we reviewed a 1948 publication discussing Stanford University's policy of withholding treatment from older adults with latent syphilis (Blum & Barnett, 1948). The rationale for the policy was that the value of penicillin for treating latent syphilis hadn't yet been conclusively proven. Armed with the hindsight knowledge that penicillin *is* safe and effective for treating latent syphilis, one could argue that Stanford's medical withholding policy inadvertently caused the deaths of dozens of syphilis patients. A more modern example of the medical withholding problem is a policy that denied shingles vaccines to people born prior to an arbitrary birth date (Taquet et al., 2024). The randomized natural experiment revealed that people who were denied the shingles vaccine suffered increased risk of developing dementia. We should strive to avoid repeating this type of error (C. Buck, 2023a, 2023c). While the research community is pursuing conclusive proof of medical efficacy, people should be allowed to decide which medical cost/risk/benefit balance is right for them, as individuals (C. B. Buck, 2023).

The existing regulatory framework in the US empowers food producers to sell innovative new foods. There have been recent "rulemaking" proposals under which regulators would override statutory language and require laborious government pre-approval processes for any new food innovation (Harrison et al., 2025; Makary, 2025). These proposals would strip consumers of their right to buy potentially healthy foods.

Current law supports a path in which food-based vaccine development could be simplified to the point that free market forces, combined with standard scientific scrutiny, could serve as a check-and-balance against regulatory overreach (Buck, 2024a, 2024b). It could be helpful for the research community, including independent scientists, to begin exploring the question of whether

results with BKV can be extended to edible vaccines covering emerging threats, such as H5N1 influenza or current SARS-CoV-2 variants.

Colleagues have expressed the concern that because vaccines are typically considered drugs, they should only be developed under the authority of the FDA drug approval process. This concern overlooks the fact that many foods are known to have drug-like medicinal properties, but the existence of medicinal properties doesn't make a food a drug unless the manufacturer makes claims to that effect. It might help to consider an analogy. When Chris's 23andMe results indicated that he has polymorphisms associated with risk of macular degeneration, he became interested in scientific literature suggesting that a GRAS food ingredient called zeaxanthin might help mitigate the possible risk. He was impressed when his ophthalmologist advised him to consider eating zeaxanthin-rich foods, such as spinach. There was even a brief discussion concerning which cooking methods seem most likely to increase zeaxanthin bioavailability. Chris may or may not be at actual risk of macular degeneration - and spinach may or may not be an effective treatment - but that doesn't mean the ophthalmologist was reckless to recommend it. It also doesn't mean Chris must file an IRB proposal or an Investigational New Drug application before growing spinach for his family, and it doesn't mean supermarkets should consider moving spinach to the pharmaceutical aisle. Extending the thought experiment, a new strain of spinach engineered to produce extra zeaxanthin could still be marketed as a food - so long as there aren't label claims about prevention of macular degeneration or other diseases. The point of the analogy is that vaccine beer, like spinach, can immediately be marketed as a potentially healthful food in full compliance with federal law.

The ophthalmologist is right. People should be empowered to exercise their right to self-experiment with healthy foods (Buck, 2022).

Appendix A. Human subjects considerations.

State and federal laws mandate that research involving human subjects must be pre-approved by an Institutional Review Board (IRB). Section [45 CFR § 46.102\(I\)](#) of the federal Common Rule offers a restricted legal definition of the term research:

*Research means a **systematic** investigation, including research development, testing, and evaluation, designed to develop or contribute to **generalizable** knowledge.*

There is ongoing public debate about how the terms “systematic” and “generalizable” (boldface ours) should be construed. At one extreme, some have argued that few investigations involving human subjects meet a strict definition of the term generalizable (Munger, 2025). The other extreme rests on the fact that the scientific method can succinctly be described as a system designed to develop generalizable knowledge. Both extremes are absurd - lawmakers can’t have intended that almost nothing requires IRB pre-review, and they can’t have intended that physicians must apply for institutional permission each time they use the scientific method in service of individual healthcare.

The Common Rule was developed based on the findings of the [Belmont Report](#) (NCPHSB, 1979), which describes individual healthcare practices as:

designed solely to enhance the well-being of an individual patient or client and that have a reasonable expectation of success.

There can be confusing overlap between the Common Rule definition of research and individual healthcare, in the sense that individual healthcare sometimes involves systematic investigations aimed at evaluating whether an experimental treatment protocol will be of benefit for a particular individual. The design of individual healthcare can also accommodate the development of limited amounts of generalizable knowledge and can even result in scientific publications (e.g., case reports). Another layer of confusion is that colloquial usage of the word “research” can refer to activities that are neither systematic nor generalizable.

To illustrate the problem, we can consider author CBB’s (Chris’s) efforts to share mint family herbs with friends, family, and colleagues during the covid pandemic, in the hope that eating mint might prevent or mitigate SARS-CoV-2 infection (C. B. Buck, 2023). Chris instructed volunteers to systematically implement a scaled-up version of a treatment protocol Jan and colleagues developed using an animal model system (C. Buck, 2023b; Jan et al., 2021). Everybody was encouraged to compare notes on their experiences, for the designed purpose of contributing to generalizable knowledge about whether mint might fight covid (Buck, 2024c).

To understand whether Chris's mint study meets the legal requirements for IRB review, it's important to consider the history behind the Common Rule. The ethical roots of the law were initially laid out in the 1949 [Nuremberg Code](#), which was formulated in response to Nazi medical atrocities during World War II. Nuremberg Core Principles, such as informed consent and the minimization of medical risk, remain central to the modern conduct of IRB review (Alexander, 2017).

The 1979 Belmont Report, which builds upon the foundation laid down by the Nuremberg Code, was commissioned in response to the disastrous *Tuskegee Study of Untreated Syphilis in the Negro Male* (TSUS), in which penicillin was abusively withheld from men with syphilis (Clinton, 1997; Tharrington, 2024; White, 2000). The medical-withholding abuse arose, in part, from a conflict between institutional research priorities and the right to access individual healthcare.

In the 1940s, it was unclear whether penicillin would be safe and effective for treating syphilis. A pioneering study by Mahoney and colleagues used an experimental protocol, scaled up from an animal model, to treat four syphilis patients (Mahoney et al., 1943). If we imagine a scenario in which Mahoney and colleagues paused the investigation to seek IRB pre-approval, it would have resulted in the risky withholding of penicillin from four syphilis patients. This cannot be the type of outcome the framers of the Common Rule intended to produce because medical withholding is exactly what the Common Rule was intended to prevent.

Clinical investigations designed to produce highly generalizable knowledge systematically include control groups. FDA guidance makes extensive use of the concept that control groups are a hallmark of generalizable research (FDA et al., 2013). A central lesson of the TSUS disaster is that studies with negative control groups (where treatment is withheld) are especially deserving of institutional pre-review.

Individual healthcare can include crossover controls (where a patient first tries one treatment and later tries another), but it never includes a control group. Therefore, we propose that study designs that lack a control group and meet the Belmont Report's description of individual healthcare are not legally required to solicit IRB review. Under this interpretation, Chris's mint study and the Mahoney study are both insufficiently systematic/generalizable to meet the legal requirement for IRB review.

The purpose of the treatments in the current study is to immunize ourselves against BK polyomavirus, with the hope that it might safely minimize our risk of polyomavirus-induced disease. When designing the study protocol, we anticipated that the experiments might produce limited amounts of generalizable knowledge. We do not view this as a valid standard for

triggering IRB review because individual healthcare, which the Belmont Report explicitly excludes from the definition of human subjects research, sometimes results in published data and case studies. Additionally, delaying an individual healthcare investigation while soliciting IRB review would constitute a form of medical withholding. The lack of a control group in the current study means there is no risk of the type of medical withholding abuse the Common Rule is designed to prevent. In support of our interpretation that individual healthcare experiments are insufficiently systematic/generalizable to meet the restricted legal definition of human subjects research, most IRBs judge these types of experiments as outside their purview (Hanley et al., 2019).

The control-based standard cuts both ways. Recent covid vaccine policy has systematically assigned millions of Americans to a *de facto* negative control group. The controlled natural experiment will contribute to generalizable knowledge by experimentally testing the hypothesis that the vaccine is of no net benefit to the involuntary study subjects from whom it is being withheld. This poorly designed withholding trial should have been pre-reviewed by an IRB.

Institutional obstruction of individual access to healthcare – particularly if it qualifies as self-care – fails to fulfill the Common Rule’s intent of preventing the central abuse of TSUS. Instead, it replicates the abuse by withholding medicine from people who might experience net benefit. In cases where such abuse appears to be happening, investigators are within their rights to instead consult family, friends, colleagues, and physicians when choosing which scientific experiments to do with their own bodies.

In addition to being an individual human right, self-experimentation can also be valuable to the collective interests of humanity by enabling rapid testing of new ideas. There is a long tradition physicians and scientists using self-experimentation to speed the process of making lifesaving discoveries (Hanley et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 1985). For these reasons, we view institutional obstruction of self-experimentation as unethical.

Appendix B. Marketing and regulatory considerations

In order for an ingredient to be marketed as food in the US, it must be Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS), as defined by federal statute [21 CFR § 170.30\(b\) and \(c\)\(1\)](#).

General recognition of safety through experience based on common use in food prior to January 1, 1958, shall be based solely on food use of the substance prior to January 1, 1958, and shall ordinarily be based upon generally available data and information. An ingredient not in common use in food prior to January 1, 1958, may achieve general recognition of safety only through scientific procedures... General recognition of safety through scientific procedures shall be based upon the application of generally available and accepted scientific data, information, or methods, which ordinarily are published, as well as the application of scientific principles, and may be corroborated by the application of unpublished scientific data, information, or methods.

Food manufacturers may choose to notify the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of a self-conducted GRAS determination, but the law does not require formal notification (FDA, 2017).

Saccharomyces cerevisiae yeast have served as a foundational food ingredient for millennia. In recent years, American consumers have quietly embraced genetically modified (GMO) yeast as a commercial beer ingredient (Kramer, 2023). The FDA has [acknowledged](#) GRAS notifications for a number of GMO yeast products.

BKV VP1 is frequently shed in human urine, and various cultures have historically engaged in the routine practice of drinking urine (Savica et al., 2011). Although the proposed health benefits of urophagia are unproven, urine and its constituent components are not known to be allergenic or toxic. Furthermore, chronic infections with BKV, and its close relative JCV, are highly prevalent and both viruses have been reported to asymptotically inhabit human gut mucosa (Shadbash et al., 2024). Recombinant VLPs composed of JCV VP1 have been tested as an experimental injection vaccine and the vaccine was well tolerated (Ray et al., 2015; Sospedra et al., 2014). We are not aware of any evidence indicating that eating VP1 as a food ingredient might be allergenic, toxic, or in other ways harmful.

The VP1 expression plasmid used in this work, pGustiv, encodes a formaldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (FDH1) gene as a selectable marker. The FDH1 sequence is derived from *Candida maltosa*, a yeast species that is non-pathogenic, commonly found in fermented dairy products, and used for industrial production of animal feed (de Melo Pereira et al., 2022; Mauersberger et al., 1996). As detailed in the Supplemental Methods section, residual levels of formaldehyde in the finished

vaccine beer are well within levels declared safe in World Health Organization guidance (WHO, 2005).

The pGustiv plasmid encodes a variant of enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP) that is useful for confirming the co-expression of vaccine antigens of interest. Dietary GFP has been shown to be safe in animal models (Han et al., 2015; Richards et al., 2003) and [online videos](#) depict home hobbyists drinking and sharing beer made from yeast expressing GFP, with no apparent adverse effects. A Phase I clinical trial (NCT009794131) concluded that a therapeutic virus expressing GFP is safe for use in humans (Jaime et al., 2012).

These scientific considerations support the determination that yeast carrying the pGustiv expression plasmid are a GRAS food.

In the future, academic groups or commercial entities may wish to file Investigational New Drug (IND) applications covering formal research investigations into the possible therapeutic efficacy of food vaccines. US law allows GRAS ingredients to be marketed as food products, so long as they were marketed as a food or dietary supplement prior to any IND applications. FDA guidance states:

Generally, the dietary supplement definition excludes ingredients that are approved as new drugs, licensed as biologics, or authorized for clinical investigation under an investigational new drug application (IND) that has gone into effect, unless the ingredient was previously marketed as a dietary supplement or as a food (FDA, 2024).

To establish a documented example of vaccine yeast being marketed as a food product, Remy LLC sold yeast slurries as food products for personal use to two customers who happen to be professional research scientists with expertise in virology and vaccine development. Both customers are former employees of the FDA. Remy LLC did not make any claims of therapeutic effects or possible structure/function health benefits. The customers have not reported any adverse effects.

Supplemental Methods

A. Simplified Vaccine Beer Production

Homebrewing is a 10,000 year-old technology that can easily be practiced in low-resource settings. This simplified protocol assumes that an inexperienced homebrewer has a pouch of transformed yeast (which can be generated using the Yeast Transformation protocol in Section C below) and wishes to produce a food vaccine in the simplest possible way using only basic kitchen equipment. The simplified beer isn't going to win any tasting competitions but drinking it (or eating the sedimented live yeast slurry it produces) should still be a reasonably pleasant experience.

Author CBB (Chris) used the simplified protocol for a booster batch. Both authors used the more complex Hopped and Bottled Vaccine Beer Production protocol (Section E) for all other batches. Both protocols produce ~1 gallon (4 L) of beer.

Gene expression from the pGustiv plasmid used in this work is suppressed by glucose and activated by maltose. Maltose makes up roughly 50% of the dry mass malt extract, while glucose accounts for 20%. This sets up a situation where yeast pitched into ordinary brewer's malt extract broth will initially replicate using glucose, which will suppress the potentially burdensome expression of green fluorescent protein (GFP) and vaccine antigens. Once the glucose is exhausted, the yeast will automatically begin to overexpress the vaccine antigen and attendant GFP marker. Successful vaccine antigen expression can be confirmed by looking for green color in beer illuminated by a blue LED and viewed through orange sunglasses. GFP expression can also be discerned as a light-green hue in live yeast sediment under ordinary room light with no filters.

Equipment

- **5 quart (~5 L) fermenter** - [Cultures For Health Continuous Brewing Jar](#)
- **Blue-light blocking glasses with blue LED light** (optional) - [SleepZM glasses](#)

Supplies

- **Malt extract** - [Breiss Golden Light Dry Malt Extract \(1 lb\)](#)
- **Yeast slurry** - Pouch of wheat ale yeast transformed with pGustiv

Steps

- 1) Any roughly gallon-size vessel can serve as a fermenter, but the spigot on the recommended Continuous Brewing Jar makes serving easier.
- 2) Since the beer will be consumed before spontaneous fermentation organisms have time to grow out, it is not strictly necessary to sanitize the fermenter.
- 3) Pour about a quart (liter) of water into the fermenter. This liquid can be tap water that has been filtered or boiled to remove chlorine. Bottled water works too.
- 4) Add about one pound (0.5 kg) of dry malt extract to the fermenter and give the mixture a bit of a swirl.
- 5) Pour in about three more quarts of water. It's important to leave plenty of headspace in the fermenter because the yeast will generate a foamy head (krausen) during fermentation. If there is too little headspace the krausen will messily overflow the fermenter.
- 6) Squeeze and gently invert the yeast pouch a few times. Add the suspended yeast slurry to the fermenter and incubate it at room temperature.
- 7) A thick krausen should form within 24 hours. If orange sunglasses and a blue light are available, the krausen and the yeast sediment at the bottom of the fermenter should begin to look vivid green under subdued room lighting within 48 hours. At this point, you can swirl the yeast into suspension using a kitchen spoon and begin to enjoy a pint or two of beer (with suspended live yeast) each day.
- 8) When the krausen subsides, move the fermenter into the refrigerator. Continue drinking suspended live yeast beer daily until it's gone.
- 9) If your goal is only to eat live yeast and not drink beer, then wait for the refrigerated yeast to settle to the bottom of the fermenter. Then pour the liquid beer (supernatant) down the drain, saving just the yeast sediment at the bottom. Experiments with mice suggest that vaccine yeast retain immunogenicity after they're dried down. This drying could make it easier to store and ship the yeast. Yeast sediment can be dried down by spreading it on a baking sheet lined with parchment paper and setting it in front of a fan for a couple of days. The dried yeast can be broken into chips and eaten directly or mixed with maltose-rich foods, such as cooled sweet potatoes or pancakes (see below). It's conceivable that rehydrating the dried yeast prior to consumption would be more effective, but this hypothesis has not yet been experimentally tested in mice.

10) ¡Salud, dinero, amor y tiempo para disfrutarlos!

B. Eating Strategies

•**Antacids:** Some pilot experiments used [famotidine](#) or calcium carbonate [antacid tablets](#) to neutralize stomach acid. Since the presence of food can transiently neutralize stomach pH, we reason that the famotidine/antacid approach might be particularly valuable when drinking actively fermenting vaccine beer on an empty stomach. For some doses, beer was consumed on an empty stomach and then chased with a pint or two of water, in hopes of quickly flushing stomach contents into the small intestine.

•**Dietary fats:** It might hypothetically be good to eat a fatty meal alongside vaccine beer to promote the secretion of bile salts that help break open the vaccine yeast in the duodenum. A mutually exclusive hypothesis is that it might be better for yeast to transiently establish residency in the gut microbiome, in which case increased secretion of bile salts would be detrimental.

•**Enteric delivery:** Although we have not experimented with the approach, it's conceivable that loading yeast slurry or dried yeast powder into [enteric capsules](#) would improve immunogenicity. Note that there have been instances reported of fungemia associated with use of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. *bouardii* probiotic supplements by immunocompromised individuals (Rannikko et al., 2021).

•**Gut fermentation.** The high-maltose recipes that we experimented with are listed below.

Pancakes: Whole wheat flour contains amylases that gradually convert starches into maltose. Amylase activity can be augmented by adding [diastatic malt powder](#), but this isn't strictly necessary unless the recipe is reformulated to only use all purpose flour (which contains very low levels of amylases).

Wheat amylases have a pH optimum of about 5 and show increased activity up to a temperature of about 140°F (60°C). The recipe below exploits these features by resting the batter in a warm oven and by using yogurt, which has a pH of about 5 and contains bacteria that can thrive at temperatures up to 115°F (46°C). Yogurt bacteria can also metabolize unwanted glucose (which suppresses vaccine antigen expression) while leaving maltose intact.

Unfortunately, fermentation of lactose (the principal sugar in milk) can release a fair amount of glucose, particularly in the early stages of yogurt production. Instead of lactose-rich cow's milk, the recipe calls for unsweetened oat milk (which contains moderate amounts of maltose with relatively little glucose).

Conversion of flour starch into maltose makes it harder to achieve the usual cake-like structure of traditional pancakes. The recipe therefore calls for adding a portion of the flour after the diastatic (maltose-producing) rest. This provides a final dose of not-yet-digested starch that gives the pancake better structure

Maltose caramelizes quickly - which means the pancakes will brown a lot faster than ordinary pancakes. Too much browning produces unpleasant bitterness. The recipe therefore calls for cooking the pancakes with more flips than typical pancake recipes.

Unfortunately, traditional maple syrup and malt syrup contain quite a lot of glucose. A more suitable syrup can be made by mixing equal masses of [food-grade maltose](#) and water.

¼ cup (50 mL) Greek yogurt

1 cup (250 mL) unsweetened oat milk

⅔ cup (150 mL) whole wheat flour

1 tsp (5 mL) [diastatic malt powder](#) (optional)

⅓ cup (80 mL) all purpose flour

1 tsp (5 mL) [yeast extract](#) (or ¼ tsp (1 mL) salt)

1 tsp (5 mL) baking powder

½ tsp (2.5 mL) baking soda

1 large egg

Vegetable oil

Butter (optional)

Maltose syrup (optional)

- 1) Preheat oven to ~170°F.
- 2) Mix together yogurt and oat milk in an oven-safe bowl. Mix in the whole wheat flour.
- 3) Cover the batter with a silicone lid (or aluminum foil) and set in the oven. Turn the oven off and let the batter rest in the oven for 2 hours.

- 4) Mix together the all-purpose flour, salt, baking powder, and baking soda. Pour the dry ingredient mixture on top of the batter.
- 5) Break up the egg with a whisk or a fork and mix into the batter until small lumps remain. Let the batter rest for five or so minutes.
- 6) While the batter is resting, pre-heat a griddle or frying pan over medium heat. Add a tablespoon or so of vegetable oil
- 7) Use a 1/3rd cup measure to pour pancakes onto the griddle. Cook for two minutes or until stable bubble holes become visible on the top of the pancake. Flip the pancake and cook for two minutes. It may be necessary to flip one or two more times to complete the cooking, depending on the temperature and the type of pan being used.
- 8) Serve with butter, maltose syrup, and a traditional Bavarian breakfast hefeweizen vaccine beer.
- 9) *Auf deine Gesundheit!*

Sweet potatoes: Sweet potatoes contain alpha and beta amylases that cooperate to convert starches primarily into maltose while producing very little glucose. The optimal temperature for maltose conversion in sweet potatoes is 60-75°C (140-167°F). The recipe calls for pre-heating the sweet potato at a low oven temperature to promote maltose conversion.

- 1) Bake a sweet potato at 170°F for one hour.
- 2) Raise the temperature to 425°F and bake for another hour until the internal temperature is 205-212°F.
- 3) Cut the sweet potato in half and enjoy it with a nice pint of vaccine beer.
- 4) *Bé salāmatee!*

•**Oral delivery:** In mouse models, sublingual or gingival delivery can be effective (Ingrole et al., 2025). It's conceivable that swishing vaccine beer around the mouth and then brushing or flossing would be helpful. Chaotropic detergents, such as the sodium dodecyl sulfate used in most brands of toothpaste, might be useful for lysing yeast to release the vaccine antigen. On the other hand, it's possible to imagine that chaotropic detergents might partially denature VLPs in a way that would impair their antigenicity.

•**Yeast dormancy:** When yeast complete a fermentation, they begin to construct thicker cell walls and activate other metabolic changes that help them hunker down to wait for fresh sugar sources to return. Yeast that have entered dormancy are more resistant to insults such as stomach

acid. From this perspective, the best approach might be to drink completed vaccine beer that has been stored in the refrigerator for a couple of days alongside a low-sugar/low-starch meal. That way yeast will remain dormant for their passage through the stomach and will not attempt to re-enter a more fragile active fermentation state. There's also an opposing hypothesis: that dormant yeast are so sturdy that they pass through the gut into the feces and never release the vaccine antigen. In this case, green beer that's still actively fermenting might be the best bet.

C. Yeast Transformation

This section describes methods for introducing plasmid DNA encoding vaccine antigens into ordinary commercial yeast strains. The transformed yeast can be used to homebrew vaccine beer that can be immunogenic if simply consumed in the form of a cloudy wheat ale containing delicious live yeast. The procedures have been simplified to the point that they can be conducted in an ordinary kitchen outfitted with minimal scientific equipment.

Yeast are first transformed with a “Gusto” plasmid encoding enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP) as a marker for a co-expressed vaccine antigen – such as the VP1 capsid protein of BK polyomavirus genotype IV ([pGustiv](#)). Hobbyists [equipped](#) for standard molecular biology manipulations can order synthetic DNA fragments encoding vaccine-related genes of interest and recombine the fragments into Gusto-series expression plasmids or other yeast expression systems.

Gusto plasmids encode a formaldehyde dehydrogenase gene that allows for selection of stably transformed yeast. Although formaldehyde is a carcinogen that should be handled with care, normal human physiology is good at detoxifying formaldehyde. The WHO sets a maximum tolerable [level](#) of 0.09 mM formaldehyde for foods and beverages. Surprisingly, a typical apple [contains](#) about 0.5 mM formaldehyde. If you go to a beauty parlor and ask for a Brazilian blowout, the beauticians put 4 M formaldehyde stock solution on your hair. In the case at hand, if a 50 mL starter culture with a typical selective dose of 6 mM formaldehyde is transferred directly into a 4 L batch of beer, then dilution alone brings the formaldehyde concentration in the finished beer within WHO safety limits. Furthermore, the formaldehyde dehydrogenase gene expressed by transformed yeast rapidly depletes formaldehyde from the culture medium. Most importantly, the protocol calls for spinning yeast out of formaldehyde-selective broth prior to transfer into the fermenter.

Homebrewers can choose from among several yeast strains that perform well for vaccine production. The simplest choice is Fermentis [WB-06](#) wheat ale yeast, which conveniently comes in stable dry form as a component of the [Flash Hefeweizen kit](#) used for producing gallon-sized batches. WB-06 is easy to transform, gives high expression of GFP and vaccine antigen, maintains Gusto plasmids well even in the absence of formaldehyde selection, is less prone to

biofilm effects, and produces a delicious cloudy suspended live yeast beer. White Labs Pakruojis ([WLP4047](#)) and Omega Jovaru ([OYL-033](#)) are similarly easy to handle and produce even more delicious cloudy beers, particularly when fermented at higher temperatures.

Experiments with mice indicate that sedimented live yeast can retain immunogenicity after air-drying them onto food pellets. Citizen scientists who prefer not to drink beer could choose Fleischmann's [Active Dry](#) bread yeast, which is easy to transform, highly flocculant, and readily dryable.

The Yeast Transformation protocol assumes the availability of limited scientific equipment and a basic knowledge of [good laboratory practice](#). Odin's [Complete Genetic Engineering Home Lab](#) or [CRISPR kits](#) provide affordable one-stop shopping for much of the essential equipment, and the internet abounds with practical tutorials.

Equipment and Supply links indicate the specific brands used for our pilot batches. Other brands could be cheaper or easier to use, and the protocols could theoretically be macgyvered to work in a kitchen without any specialized lab equipment.

Equipment

- **Orbital thermomixer** - [UltraVen DHS-100](#)
- **2 mL Screw-cap tubes** - [Biologix 2.0 mL Crovials](#)
- **Micropipettors and tips** - [Odin kits](#)
- **Microcentrifuge** - [Lchoi Mini Lab Centrifuge](#)
- **Centrifuge capable of handling 50 mL tubes** - [Lab Fish LC 500](#)
- **50 mL centrifuge tubes** - [Cbtone 50 mL tubes with screw cap](#)
- **Petri dishes** - [Odin kits](#)
- **Inoculation loop** - [Hajxch 10 µL inoculation loop](#)
- **Incubator** (optional) - [Ivyx 5 L Incubator](#)
- **Heated stir plate** - [Hycc Magnetic Stirrer Hot Plate](#)
- **50 mL Erlenmeyer flask** - [MoreBeer 50 mL Erlenmeyer flask](#)
- **1 L Erlenmeyer flask** - [MoreBeer 1000 mL Erlenmeyer flask](#)
- **Vortex mixer** (optional) - [Lchoi Mini Vortex Mixer](#)
- **Blue-light blocking glasses with blue LED light** (optional) - [SleepZM glasses](#)

Supplies

- **1 µg yeast expression plasmid** - [pGustiv plasmid](#)
- **YPD broth** - [KD Medical YPD Broth](#)
- **YPD-agar** - [KD Medical YPD Agar](#)
- **Small amount of dried yeast or commercial yeast slurry**
- **Transformation Buffer** - [Odin Yeast Transformation Kit](#)

- **Formaldehyde solution** - [Sigma Aldrich F8775](#)
- **Parafilm** - [Bemis Parafilm](#)
- **Culture dishes** - [Odin kits](#)
- **Malt extract plates** - [Olympus Myco MYA Plate](#)
- **Yeast extract** (optional) - [Make It Meaty Savory Premium](#)
- **Storage pouches** (optional) - [GUXACU Travel Pouches](#)

Steps

1. Transfer a few grains of dried yeast (or a few microliters of commercial yeast slurry) into a 2mL screw-cap tube containing 250 μ l of YPD broth. Yeast cultures at this stage benefit from exposure to oxygen. Partially unscrew the lid of the tube and apply a small piece of tape to one side of the lid to stop it from screwing closed while shaking. Shake the culture at 750 rpm at 30°C (86°F) for a couple of hours. Some individual yeast strains may work better at other incubation temperatures ranging from 18-37°C (64-99°F).
2. Put 250 μ l of fresh YPD broth in a 2mL tube and then add 10 μ l of the initial slurry. Shake at appropriate temperature until culture is nearly opaque (OD₆₀₀ 0.5-1.0). This should take several hours. If you overshoot and the culture becomes completely opaque, then transfer 50 μ l of the late-log phase culture into 250 μ l of fresh YPD broth and culture for a couple hours to get the yeast back into early-log phase.
3. Spin yeast for 3 min at \sim 700 x g (3500 rpm in a microcentrifuge with a 5 cm rotor).
4. Remove supernatant and add 50 μ l of Odin Transformation Buffer to the tube. Resuspend the cells by briefly vortexing or flicking the tube.
5. Pipet about 0.5 μ g of plasmid to the yeast suspension and suspend the cells by gently flicking the tube or by trituration (pipetting up and down). Note that the transformation buffer is very viscous.
6. Incubate the culture at 30°C (86°F) for an hour. Either apply gentle shaking (250 rpm) or flick the tube to resuspend the cells several times during the incubation.
7. Heat shock the cells by raising the temperature to 42°C (108°F) for 8 minutes. The standard Odin protocol recommends an hour at 42°C. Although the longer heat shock works well for most yeast strains, it kills some temperature-sensitive strains (e.g., English ale yeast). The 8 minute heat shock is a good compromise.
8. Add 500 μ l of fresh YPD and shake at 30°C (86°F) for a few hours.

9. Spin recovered yeast cells out of the YPD/transformation mix and discard the supernatant.
10. Resuspend the recovered cells in 250 μ l of fresh YPD. Add an appropriate dose of formaldehyde based on yeast strain (see Table S1 of forthcoming NCI manuscript). For example, pre-dilute 37% (13.4 M) formaldehyde stock solution 1:20 in YPD to make an intermediate stock solution. Then add 2.2 μ l of the intermediate stock to the yeast suspension to get the final 6 mM concentration appropriate for wheat ale yeast.
11. Shake the culture overnight at 30°C. It's important that the cells remain in suspension during the recovery to mitigate biofilm effects (see forthcoming NCI manuscript).
12. Pour YPD-formaldehyde plates
 - Formaldehyde plates gradually lose potency over the course of a week of storage at 4°C, so it's best to pour the selective plates within a day or so of when they will be used.
 - Partially melt YPD-agar in a microwave.
 - Pipet or pour 30 mL of molten agar into a 50 mL centrifuge tube.
 - Partially cool the agar by swirling the sealed tube under cold tap water for a minute.
 - Add a dose of formaldehyde appropriate for the yeast strain you are using. For example, add 13 μ l of 37% (13.4 M) formaldehyde stock solution to get a 6 mM final concentration appropriate for selecting wheat ale yeast. Invert the tube a few times to mix and then let the tube sit for a minute to let bubbles subside.
 - Pipet or pour the agar into a petri dish. Allow the dish to cool and solidify with the lid ajar.
13. Spin recovered yeast cells down in a microcentrifuge and discard supernatant. Briefly vortex to suspend cells in residual fluid then use an inoculation loop to [streak](#) most of the pelleted cell slurry onto a YPD-formaldehyde plate.
14. Incubate the plate at 30°C for 1-3 days until colonies appear.
15. Use an inoculation loop to pick half a dozen of the largest colonies from the most distal section of the streak into 250 μ l of YPD-formaldehyde, then shake for a few hours. Picking multiple colonies reduces the chance of unwanted genetic bottlenecking effects.
16. Streak the liquid culture onto a malt extract plate. Incubate the plate at 30°C for two days.

17. Expression driven by the MAL32 promoter in Gusto series plasmids can be verified by looking for the presence of enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP). If GFP is present, the colonies will appear green when wearing blue-light blocking (i.e., orange) sunglasses and shining a blue light on them. Note that the enhanced GFP used in Gusto-series plasmids fluoresces under blue light, not UV. As the colonies grow larger they should develop an eerie green color to the naked eye under ordinary room light.
18. Pick half a dozen of the largest and greenest colonies into 250 μ l of YPD-formaldehyde and shake for a few hours.
19. The malt extract plate can serve as an archive during the two-month interval between the prime and boost vaccine doses. Archived plates should be sealed with parafilm or placed in a ziplock bag. If a deep-freeze is available, a final concentration of ~18% glycerol can be added to a YPD-formaldehyde culture that has been shaken overnight to reach stationary phase. Ideally, the glycerol stock should be frozen slowly (e.g. in a Mr. Frosty cryo cooler or wrapped in paper towels). Glycerol stocks can be stored for years.
20. Place 20 mL of YPD broth and a stir bar into a 50 mL Erlenmeyer flask and cover with aluminum foil. Sterilize the flask in a pressure cooker. If a pressure cooker isn't available then sanitize only the flask and the YPD using a microwave. Do not microwave the metal stir bar or foil - use a sanitizer instead (see Beer Production protocol below). Pay careful attention while microwaving to avoid foam-overs.
21. Allow the YPD to cool to room temperature and then add an appropriate dose of formaldehyde. Add the 250 μ l YPD-formaldehyde culture to the flask and stir overnight until the culture is opaque.
22. Expand the 20 mL culture by pouring into 200 mL of YPD-formaldehyde in a sterilized or sanitized 1 L Erlenmeyer flask. Culture until opaque (6-12 hours).
23. Centrifuge the 200 mL starter culture in six 50 mL tubes for 5 min at 700 x g (~2400 rpm in a LAB FISH centrifuge with 12 cm rotor). Don't be tempted to fill four 50 mL tubes to the brim because liquid may leak out from the top of the tube during the fixed-angle spin. It's theoretically possible to use a microcentrifuge for this step by performing multiple spins in 2 mL tubes, but it would be laborious, the repeated centrifugation would be hard on the yeast cells, and the repeated opening and closing of tubes would increase the risk of introducing spoilage organisms.
24. Pour the YPD-formaldehyde supernatant out of the 50 mL tubes. The yeast is ready to be used in step 6 of either the Simplified or Hopped and Bottled Beer Production protocols.

Alternatively, if not proceeding to beer production immediately, the yeast can be suspended in 20 mL of sterile water with a pinch of food-grade yeast extract (provides nutrients and salt). Stored yeast produce carbon dioxide, which creates high pressure in sealed containers, so the slurry should be stored in expandable plastic storage pouches. The stored slurry should last at least six weeks in the fridge.

D. Determining formaldehyde sensitivity

Different yeast strains have different innate levels of susceptibility to formaldehyde. There is also a hidden variable to be aware of - some yeast strains are able to form biofilms that make them highly resistant to formaldehyde. Formaldehyde-resistant biofilms can form if a liquid culture is allowed to settle or if the yeast are spread onto agar plates at high density. The reason the main protocol initially selects transformed yeast in shaken liquid culture is to enrich for successful transformants to the point that individual green colonies will be observed far out into the lower density regions of a streaked plate (where biofilm effects are minimal).

The purpose of this sub-protocol is to determine the susceptibility of a given yeast strain to formaldehyde in shaken liquid culture or at low density on agar plates.

- 1) Culture yeast in YPD broth until cloudy ($OD_{600} \sim 0.5-1.0$). This should typically correspond to a live cell density of about 5×10^4 per μl . A stationary culture is closer to 2×10^5 per μl .
- 2) If only one yeast strain is being tested, set up a series of 100 μl YPD liquid cultures with 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, or 10 mM formaldehyde in 2 ml tubes. Transfer 1 μl of late-log yeast culture into each tube and shake vigorously overnight.
- 3) If many yeast strains are being tested, pour separate YPD-agar plates with 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, or 10 mM formaldehyde.
- 4) Perform a 1:1000 dilution of the late-log yeast culture (or two 1:100 dilutions if stationary culture is used) into YPD.

- 5) Spot 5 μl of diluted culture onto agar. A grid can be drawn onto the plate and up to two dozen different yeast strains can be tested at once.
- 6) Grow liquid culture (or plates) at 30°C for two days.
- 7) Record the lowest formaldehyde concentration at which there are no colonies.

E. Hopped and Bottled Vaccine Beer Production

This somewhat more complicated beer production protocol produces tastier beer that can be kept and distributed in a bottled form. Just like the Simplified Beer Production protocol, the protocol below produces ~1 gallon (4 L) of beer.

New brewers may benefit from watching a quick how-to [video](#) for the [Flash Brewing kit](#) that serves as a foundation for the protocol.

For millennia, weak beer has served as a safer alternative to drinking-water in low-resource settings. Although the ethanol and acids produced during beer fermentation suppress the growth of a wide range of pathogens, beer can still be a home for spoilage organisms that, while not particularly harmful, may not be very tasty. Competition from spoilage organisms can also reduce yeast health.

Home brewers can use a variety of strategies to avoid introducing spoilage organisms into the fermenter. The first, and most obvious, is the boiling process embodied in the word “brew.” Some pieces of equipment (most notably, larger fermenters) can’t easily be subjected to an extended boil - so chemical sanitization is typically used to prepare these items. One example of a sanitizing agent is Powdered Brewery Wash ([PBW](#)). Another simple approach is to use 70% ethanol. There are a wide range of [videos](#) available online demonstrating basic sanitization methods. One place that our protocol differs from other sources is that our pilot production experiments routinely washed away sanitizing agents using boiled hot water - even for supposedly no-rinse products. Yeast health is of paramount importance for vaccine beer production and we didn’t want to take any chances with sanitizer residues.

One departure from common sanitization protocols is that we did not perform culture operations next to the traditional open flame. In our opinion, the sanitization benefits of an open flame are outweighed by its safety risk. A [Coway Airmega](#) air filter was run in the home lab environment, in hopes of reducing the level of suspended spoilage organisms in the air.

Sanitization is especially important in the early stages of fermentation, before the yeast have established an antibacterial environment with >3% ethanol. Sanitization is less of an issue if a large number of healthy yeast cells are pitched into the fermenter, with the theory being that the high cell count gives rapid establishment of antibacterial conditions.

Fortunately, the growth of spoilage organisms in finished beer is relatively slow. Since vaccine beer will generally be consumed soon after completion of fermentation, spoilage should be less of a problem than for traditional beers intended to be kept for longer terms.

Equipment

- **5 quart (~5 L) fermenter** - [Cultures For Health Continuous Brewing Jar](#)
- **Tape thermometer** - [JIYIN Aquarium Tape Thermometer](#)
- **French press** - [Utopia 17oz French Press](#)
- **Beer bottles** - [EZ Cap Swing Top Bottles](#)
- **Small funnel** - [YLYL funnels](#)
- **Heated stir plate** - [HYCC Magnetic Stirrer Hot Plate](#)
- **Blue-light blocking glasses with blue LED light** (optional) - [SleepZM glasses](#)
- **Hydrometer** (optional) - [MoreBeer MT312](#)
- **Pipettor** - [Onilab Pipette Pump](#)
- **Pipettes** - [SciStar 25 mL Serological Pipettes](#)

Supplies

- **Flash Brewing kit** - [MoreBeer Flash Hefeweizen](#)
- **Hops** (optional) - [Artisan Saphir pellets](#)
- **Yeast slurry from Yeast Transformation section (above)**
- **Malt extract starter broth** - [Omega Yeast Labs Proper Starter](#)
- **Sanitizer** - [70% food-grade ethanol](#) and/or [PBW tablets](#)
- **Food-grade maltose** (optional) - [Lab Alley Maltose, NF Grade](#)
- **Endoprotease enzyme** (optional) - [White Labs Clarity Ferm](#)
- **Automotive coolant** (optional) - [Valvoline Prediluted 50/50 Antifreeze](#)

Steps

- 1) Sanitize a 5 quart (~5 L) fermenter using 70% ethanol, PBW, or other sanitizing product (see manufacturer instructions or [MoreBeer.com video](#)). Open the fermenter sidearm (spigot) so that some of the sanitizer can enter it. An optional step is to rinse away

residual sanitizer by pouring some boiled hot water (e.g., from a tea kettle) into the fermenter and swirling it around. Discard the rinse water and then close the sidearm.

- 2) Sanitize the top of a can of concentrated Propper starter broth and pour the entire contents of the can into the fermenter. Dilute by adding one pint (~0.5 L) of boiled water to the fermenter.
- 3) Stick a tape thermometer horizontally on the outside of the fermenter near the bottom (below the level of the diluted Propper starter liquid). If necessary, chill the fermenter to reach suitable fermentation temperature (e.g., around 75°F/24°C for wheat ale yeast). Too high a temperature can damage or kill the yeast.
- 4) Sanitize a stir bar (using ethanol, sanitizer, or boiling) and add it to the fermenter. Turn the stir plate on low. Angle a corner of the fermenter onto a stir plate until you can hear that the stir bar is whirling (as opposed to jumping around chaotically) then slowly slide the fermenter until it's centered on the stir plate. If the stir bar is properly seated, a shallow whirlpool should form on the surface. Because the bottom of the fermenter is convex, seating the stir bar is a challenging process that may take a few tries and may even be worth practicing ahead of time using just water in the fermenter.
- 5) Turn up the stir speed to medium-high for a few minutes to aerate the starter broth. Yeast benefit from having plenty of oxygen at this stage.
- 6) Use a 25 mL pipet and 10 mL of Propper starter broth to resuspend the yeast in the 50 mL centrifuge tubes from the final step of the Yeast Transformation protocol. If handling stored yeast, resuspend the cells by massaging and gently inverting the pouch, then squeeze the slurry into the fermenter.
- 7) Reduce stirring speed to low. Only a shallow dimple should be visible on the surface of the beer. Leave it stirring on low speed for 6-12 hours. If the ambient temperature in the room is below the fermentation temperature range for the yeast, you may need to add a bit of heat on the stir plate. However, be aware that fermentation is an exothermic process that can naturally raise the temperature by several degrees.
- 8) Add 1 pound (~0.5 kg) of Flash Hefeweizen dry malt extract to the fermenter. To weigh the malt extract, tare (zero) a kitchen scale on the entire bag of extract powder, then pour powder into the fermenter in stages until the scale reads negative 1 pound.
- 9) Add 3 quarts (~3 liters) filtered tap water to the fermenter. If filtered tap water is unavailable then either use bottled water or pre-boil ordinary tap water to remove

chlorine and to cut down on any spoilage organisms. After adding the water to the fermenter, it's OK if there are initially some clumps of malt extract floating on the top - they will dissolve over the course of an hour or two. It's important that there is a fair amount of headspace in the fermenter because the yeast will form a fluffy krausen (foam) during the ferment. Although krausen never overflowed the fermenter in any of the pilot batches, we left the lid of the fermenter on loosely (unscrewed) and placed the fermenter in a location that would be easy to clean up, just in case.

- 10) For individuals who are sensitive to gluten, White Labs Clarity Ferm can be added at this stage to enzymatically reduce gluten levels.
- 11) Put an ounce (~30 g) of Saphir hop pellets into a French press and add a pint (~0.5 L) of boiling water. If Saphir pellets (or other hops of interest) aren't available then the half-ounce packet of Hallertau hops that comes with the 2-gallon Flash Hefeweizen kit can be used instead. Let the hop tea steep until cool, then press down the hop solids. Pour the cooled filtrate into the fermenter. Don't follow the Flash kit's instructions to put hops directly into the fermenter because hop sediments will get mixed together with the live yeast, resulting in unpleasantly pulpy texture and harsh flavor. Don't use the Hop Bite syringe that comes with the Flash kit - too much of its bitterness is taken up by the live yeast, which results in a harsh-tasting suspended-live-yeast beer. Beer made without hops is reasonably palatable, so hops can be considered optional. Hops have antibacterial effects, so sanitization would be especially important for hop-free beers.
- 12) Stir the fermenting beer at low speed until the krausen (foam) subsides (2-4 days, depending on yeast strain and temperature).
- 13) Gusto plasmids, such as the pGustiv plasmid used in pilot experiments, are engineered to express enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP) at the same time they express the vaccine antigen. In other words, yeast cells in a successful vaccine beer batch will emit green light when pure blue light is shined on them. To check for fluorescence, wear orange sunglasses and shine a blue LED light at the fermenter. The sunglasses will filter out the input blue light and only let through the green fluorescence emitted by the GFP. It's easier to see the fluorescence in beer decanted into a white dish in subdued room lighting. Automobile coolant (antifreeze) typically contains fluorescein, which has a fluorescent spectrum similar to GFP. The beer should be nearly as fluorescent as the normal 50/50 working dilution of antifreeze.
- 14) When the krausen has subsided, the fermentation should be complete. The finished beer should no longer taste sweet. The completion of the fermentation can be confirmed with

an optional hydrometer reading. The finished beer is expected to have a final gravity of about 1.015, which corresponds to about 5% alcohol by volume.

- 15) When the fermentation is finished, prepare for bottling by adding food-grade maltose to the fermenter at roughly 1% weight/volume (e.g., add 40 grams of maltose to 4 liters of beer). Set the stir plate to high until the maltose is dissolved and the yeast are uniformly suspended. Note that there's a potential safety risk in this stage of homebrewing. If the beer is bottled before it's fully fermented - or if too much maltose is added - the carbonation can become so high that the bottle will explode. Even if the bottle doesn't explode, over-carbonated bottles can messily gush beer all over the place. Warm flat beer is still a reasonably pleasant beverage, so carbonation can be considered optional. Concerned novices should feel free to simply drink beer directly from the fermenter and skip the bottling step.
- 16) Sanitize eight swing-cap pint bottles and a funnel by spraying with 70% ethanol, rinsing with PBW, boiling, or running in a dishwasher cycle with heated drying and no detergent.
- 17) With the stir plate still set to high, use the sidearm/spigot to dispense the beer and suspended yeast through the funnel into the bottles.
- 18) Let the bottled beer sit at room temperature for a day or two to carbonate the beer and then refrigerate. In an initial batch of vaccine beer, GFP fluorescence declined by about 80% after six weeks in the bottle. A best guess is that vaccine beer should be consumed within a week of bottling. Drinking the beer while it's still young also reduces the risk of spoilage and gradual over-carbonation - which is of particular concern for STA1-positive yeast strains, such as Pakruojis and WB-06.
- 19) See the Eating Strategies section for serving suggestions.
- 20) *I sveikata!*

Disclosures

Author CBB (Chris) is employed by the National Cancer Institute (NCI) and is a member of the NCI team developing food-based vaccine technology. The results and ideas presented in this report exclusively represent Chris's identity as a private citizen and do not represent his views as a federal employee or the official views of NCI. This study was conducted as a personal outside healthcare activity during Chris's free time and did not use any non-public information or other government resources.

In his capacity as an NCI employee, Chris serves as an inventor on NCI patents covering traditional BKV and JCV vaccine technologies. He receives a share of the licensing royalties from these inventions. In his personal opinion, oral live yeast approaches do not fall under the claims of the NCI patents.

Author ARB (Andrew) is the founder and sole member of Remy LLC. Remy LLC is a food and supplement supplier that has no association with any government entities.

Chris and Andrew are siblings.

References

- Alexander, S. (2017). My IRB Nightmare. *Slate Star Codex*.
<https://slatestarcodex.com/2017/08/29/my-irb-nightmare/>
- Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (1979). *Principles of Biomedical Ethics* (1st ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Berkley, S. (2025). Unraveling the arc of vaccine progress. *Science*, 389(6763), eaea7053.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1126/science.aea7053>
- Blum, H. L., & Barnett, C. W. (1948). Prognosis in Late Latent Syphilis. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, 82(4), 393-409. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.1948.00020040073005>
- Buck, C. (2022). The Freedom to Choose Medicine Is a Civil Right. *Viruses Must Die*.
<https://cbuck.substack.com/p/the-freedom-to-choose-medicine-is>
- Buck, C. (2023a). Everybody Should Be Allowed to Choose the HPV Vaccine. *Viruses Must Die*(October 7). <https://cbuck.substack.com/p/everybody-should-be-allowed-to-choose>
- Buck, C. (2023b). Mint vs Covid: A Culinary Perspective. *Viruses Must Die*.
<https://cbuck.substack.com/p/mint-vs-covid-a-culinary-perspective>
- Buck, C. (2023c). We Tuskegeed My Dad. *Viruses Must Die*. <https://cbuck.substack.com/p/we-tuskegeed-my-dad>
- Buck, C. (2024a). Consumer Reports for Medicines. *Viruses Must Die*(January 14).
<https://cbuck.substack.com/p/consumer-reports-for-medicines>
- Buck, C. (2024b). Life, Liberty, and the Pursuit of Health Experiments. *Viruses Must Die*(January 13). <https://cbuck.substack.com/p/life-liberty-and-the-pursuit-of-health>
- Buck, C. (2024c). Viruses are Supervillains, Herbs are Superheroes. *Viruses Must Die*.
<https://cbuck.substack.com/p/viruses-are-supervillains-herbs-are>
- Buck, C. (2025). How to Make and Share Vaccine-Style Beer. World Vaccine Congress, Washington, DC.
- Buck, C. B. (2023). The mint versus Covid hypothesis. *Med Hypotheses*, 173.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2023.111047>
- Clinton, B. (1997). Apology For Study Done in Tuskegee [Speech].
<https://clintonwhitehouse4.archives.gov/New/Remarks/Fri/19970516-898.html>
- de Aizpurua, H. J., & Russell-Jones, G. J. (1988). Oral vaccination. Identification of classes of proteins that provoke an immune response upon oral feeding. *J Exp Med*, 167(2), 440-451. <https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.167.2.440>
- de Melo Pereira, G. V., Maske, B. L., de Carvalho Neto, D. P., Karp, S. G., De Dea Lindner, J., Martin, J. G. P., de Oliveira Hosken, B., & Soccol, C. R. (2022). What Is Candida Doing in My Food? A Review and Safety Alert on Its Use as Starter Cultures in Fermented Foods. *Microorganisms*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10091855>
- FDA. (2017). *Guidance for Industry: Regulatory Framework for Substances Intended for Use in Human Food or Animal Food on the Basis of the Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) Provision of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act*. <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/guidance-industry-regulatory-framework-substances-intended-use-human-food-or-animal-food-basis>
- FDA. (2024). Questions and Answers on Dietary Supplements.
<https://www.fda.gov/food/information-consumers-using-dietary-supplements/questions-and-answers-dietary-supplements>
- FDA, Evaluation, C. f. D., Research, Evaluation, C. f. B., Research, Safety, C. f. F., & Nutrition, A. (2013). *Investigational New Drug Applications (INDs): Determining Whether Human Research Studies Can Be Conducted Without an IND. Guidance for Clinical Investigators, Sponsors, and IRBs*. Rockville, MD: U.S. Food and Drug Administration Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/files/drugs/published/Investigational-New-Drug->

[Applications-\(INDs\)-Determining-Whether-Human-Research-Studies-Can-Be-Conducted-Without-an-IND.pdf](#)

- Han, X., Wang, L., Li, W., Li, B., Yang, Y., Yan, H., Qu, L., & Chen, Y. (2015). Use of green fluorescent protein to monitor *Lactobacillus plantarum* in the gastrointestinal tract of goats. *Braz J Microbiol*, 46(3), 849-854. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1517-838246320140556>
- Hanley, B. P., Bains, W., & Church, G. (2019). Review of Scientific Self-Experimentation: Ethics History, Regulation, Scenarios, and Views Among Ethics Committees and Prominent Scientists. *Rejuvenation Res*, 22(1), 31-42. <https://doi.org/10.1089/rej.2018.2059>
- Harrison, T. A., Lewis, C. A., & Yapp, N. (2025). FDA Announces Notice of Proposed Rulemaking to Eliminate Self-Affirmed GRAS and Revise GRAS Review Criteria. *Venable*. <https://www.venable.com/insights/publications/2025/09/fda-announces-notice-of-proposed-rulemaking-to>
- Ingrole, R. S. J., Shakya, A. K., Joshi, G., Lee, C. H., Nesovic, L. D., Compans, R. W., & Gill, H. S. (2025). Floss-based vaccination targets the gingival sulcus for mucosal and systemic immunization. *Nat Biomed Eng*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-025-01451-3>
- Jaime, J. C., Young, A. M., Mateo, J., Yap, T. A., Denholm, K. A., Shah, K. J., Tunariu, N., Sassi, S., Karapanegiotou, L., Mansfield, D., Molife, L. R., Harrington, K. J., & De Bono, J. S. (2012). Phase I clinical trial of a genetically modified and oncolytic vaccinia virus GL-ONC1 with green fluorescent protein imaging. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 30(15 suppl), 2530. https://ascopubs.org/doi/10.1200/jco.2012.30.15_suppl.2530
- Jain, H. (2025). Cottage-Core Biotech. *Mundane Beauty*. <https://www.mundane.beauty/p/cottage-core-biotech>
- Jan, J.-T., Cheng, T.-J. R., Juang, Y.-P., Ma, H.-H., Wu, Y.-T., Yang, W.-B., Cheng, C.-W., Chen, X., Chou, T.-H., Shie, J.-J., Cheng, W.-C., Chein, R.-J., Mao, S.-S., Liang, P.-H., Ma, C., Hung, S.-C., & Wong, C.-H. (2021). Identification of existing pharmaceuticals and herbal medicines as inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(5), e2021579118. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.2021579118>
- Kahl, L., Molloy, J., Patron, N., Matthewman, C., Haseloff, J., Grewal, D., Johnson, R., & Endy, D. (2018). Opening options for material transfer. *Nat Biotechnol*, 36(10), 923-927. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4263>
- Kramer, A. (2023, 2023-07-18). The Secret Ingredient in Your Craft Beer? Gene-Edited Yeast. <https://www.wired.com/story/the-secret-ingredient-in-your-craft-beer-gene-edited-yeast/>
- Kraushaar, L. (2024). Individualised Lifestyle Medicine — The FDA-Approved N-Of-1 Method To Test Drive Health Advice. *Read or Die*. <https://medium.com/read-or-die-hq/individualised-lifestyle-medicine-the-fda-approved-n-of-1-method-to-test-drive-health-advice-29e502153522>
- Lee, Y., Kim, Y. J., & Cho, H. (2019). BK virus nephropathy and multiorgan involvement in a child with heart transplantation. *Clin Nephrol*, 91(2), 107-113. <https://doi.org/10.5414/CN109520>
- Mahoney, J. F., Arnold, R. C., & Harris, A. (1943). Penicillin Treatment of Early Syphilis-A Preliminary Report. *Am J Public Health Nations Health*, 33(12), 1387-1391. <https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.33.12.1387>
- Makary, M. (2025). Statement from FDA Commissioner Marty Makary, MD, MPH: 100 Days of Embracing Gold-Standard Science, Transparency and Common Sense. <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/statement-fda-commissioner-marty-makary-md-mph-100-days-embracing-gold-standard-science-transparency>
- Marshall, B. J., Armstrong, J. A., McGeachie, D. B., & Glancy, R. J. (1985). Attempt to fulfil Koch's postulates for pyloric *Campylobacter*. *Med J Aust*, 142(8), 436-439. <https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1985.tb113443.x>

- Mastroianni, A. (2023). Let's build a fleet and change the world. *Experimental History*. <https://www.experimental-history.com/p/lets-build-a-fleet-and-change-the>
- Mauersberger, S., Ohkuma, M., Schunck, W.-H., & Takagi, M. (1996). *Candida maltosa*. In *Nonconventional Yeasts in Biotechnology: A Handbook* (pp. 411-580). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-79856-6_12
- Munger, K. (2025). Experiments as Performance Art. <https://kevinmunger.substack.com/p/experiments-as-performance-art>
- NCPHSB. (1979). *The Belmont Report: Ethical Principles and Guidelines for the Protection of Human Subjects of Research*. <https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/regulations-and-policy/belmont-report/read-the-belmont-report/index.html>
- O'Reilly, K. B. (2025). Latest ACIP move is dangerous to the nation's health. *Prevention & Wellness*. Retrieved 2025/07/31, from <https://www.ama-assn.org/public-health/prevention-wellness/latest-acip-move-dangerous-nation-s-health>
- Pecquet, S., Guillaumin, D., Tancrede, C., & Andremont, A. (1991). Kinetics of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* elimination from the intestines of human volunteers and effect of this yeast on resistance to microbial colonization in gnotobiotic mice. *Appl Environ Microbiol*, 57(10), 3049-3051. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.57.10.3049-3051.1991>
- Petrogiannis-Haliotis, T., Sakoulas, G., Kirby, J., Koralknik, I. J., Dvorak, A. M., Monahan-Earley, R., PC, D. E. G., U, D. E. G., Upton, M., Major, E. O., Pfister, L. A., & Joseph, J. T. (2001). BK-related polyomavirus vasculopathy in a renal-transplant recipient. *N Engl J Med*, 345(17), 1250-1255. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa010319>
- Pinto, M., & Dobson, S. (2014). BK and JC virus: a review. *J Infect*, 68 Suppl 1, S2-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2013.09.009>
- Rannikko, J., Holmberg, V., Karppelin, M., Arvola, P., Huttunen, R., Mattila, E., Kerttula, N., Puhto, T., Tamm, Ü., Koivula, I., Vuento, R., Syrjänen, J., & Hohenthal, U. (2021). Fungemia and Other Fungal Infections Associated with Use of *Saccharomyces boulardii* Probiotic Supplements. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 27(8), 2090-2096. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2708.210018>
- Ray, U., Cinque, P., Gerevini, S., Longo, V., Schippling, S., Martin, R., Buck, C. B., & Pastrana, D. V. (2015). JC Polyomavirus Mutants Escape Antibody-Mediated Neutralization. *Science Translational Medicine*, 7(306), 306ra151. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29091757>
- Richards, H. A., Han, C.-T., Hopkins, R. G., Failla, M. L., Ward, W. W., & Stewart, C. N. (2003). Safety Assessment of Recombinant Green Fluorescent Protein Orally Administered to Weaned Rats. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 133(6), 1909-1912. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/133.6.1909>
- Robles, M. T. S., Cantalupo, P. G., Duray, A. M., Freeland, M., Murkowski, M., van Bokhoven, A., Stephens-Shields, A. J., Pipas, J. M., & Imperiale, M. J. (2020). Analysis of viruses present in urine from patients with interstitial cystitis. *Virus Genes*, 56(4), 430-438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11262-020-01767-z>
- Sandler, E. S., Aquino, V. M., Goss-Shohet, E., Hinrichs, S., & Krisner, K. (1997). BK papova virus pneumonia following hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. *Bone Marrow Transplant*, 20(2), 163-165. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bmt.1700849>
- Savica, V., Calò, L. A., Santoro, D., Monardo, P., Mallamace, A., & Bellinghieri, G. (2011). Urine therapy through the centuries. *J Nephrol*, 24 Suppl 17, S123-125. <https://doi.org/10.5301/jn.2011.6463>
- Shadbash, P., Hosseini, S. M., Shoraka, S., Ghaemi, A., Haghazali, M., & Mohebbi, S. R. (2024). Possible association between polyomaviruses and gastrointestinal complications: a narrative review. *Gastroenterol Hepatol Bed Bench*, 17(2), 121-131. <https://doi.org/10.22037/ghfbb.v17i2.2796>

- Sills, J., Estep, P. W., & Church, G. M. (2020). Transparency is key to ethical vaccine research. *Science*, 370(6523), 1422-1423. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1126/science.abf4851>
- Sospedra, M., Schippling, S., Yousef, S., Jelcic, I., Bofill-Mas, S., Planas, R., Stellmann, J. P., Demina, V., Cinque, P., Garcea, R., Croughs, T., Girones, R., & Martin, R. (2014). Treating Progressive Multifocal Leukoencephalopathy With Interleukin 7 and Vaccination With JC Virus Capsid Protein VP1. *Clin Infect Dis*, 59(11), 1588-1592. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciu682>
- Starrett, G. J., Yu, K., Golubeva, Y., Lenz, P., Piaskowski, M. L., Petersen, D., Dean, M., Israni, A., Hernandez, B. Y., Tucker, T. C., Cheng, I., Gonsalves, L., Morris, C. R., Hussain, S. K., Lynch, C. F., Harris, R. S., Prokunina-Olsson, L., Meltzer, P. S., Buck, C. B., & Engels, E. A. (2023). Evidence for virus-mediated oncogenesis in bladder cancers arising in solid organ transplant recipients. *Elife*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.82690>
- Taquet, M., Dercon, Q., Todd, J. A., & Harrison, P. J. (2024). The recombinant shingles vaccine is associated with lower risk of dementia. *Nat Med*, 30(10), 2777-2781. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03201-5>
- Tharrington, C. (2024). *The Lost Lesson of Tuskegee*. <https://christharrington.substack.com/p/the-lost-lesson-of-tuskegee>
- White, R. M. (2000). Unraveling the Tuskegee Study of Untreated Syphilis. *Arch Intern Med*, 160(5), 585-598. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.160.5.585>
- WHO. (2005). *Formaldehyde in Drinking-water: Background document for development of WHO Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality*. Retrieved from <https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/wash-documents/wash-chemicals/formaldehyde-bd-130605.pdf>